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FROM FACTORY TO REPLICATOR

TOWARDS DESIGN METHODS FOR ON-DEMAND ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

Additive Manufacturing (AM) represents a collection of digital fabrication technologies such as Selective Laser Sintering and Fused Deposition Modeling. These means are maturing and getting widespread and some predict AM as a game changer in New Product Development. But how will designers adapt or change their way of working to a process where AM is an integrated part?

This article proposes a research approach which explores the possibilities of AM for industrial designers and New Product Development. The approach is a combination of research in design context and design inclusive research, leading to design methods and software tools.

A forerunning focus group study with design students and a senior designer confirms our hypothesis that the gap between the possibilities of AM and industrial design needs to be addressed.

Keywords: Design for Additive Manufacturing, Products On Demand.

INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is a maturing collection of technologies also known as rapid prototyping, rapid manufacturing and three-dimensional (3D-) printing. AM machines have long been available to specialized design professionals but the high price of the machines and materials used to made them all but unobtainable to small- and mid-sized firms and individuals. However, prices of the machines have been dropping and recently several sub \$2000 printers have come to the market (Wohlers, 2010).

Today, most AM applications are limited to the production of prototypes and casting inserts, since mechanical properties and surface finish are inadequate for direct use and require post processing. Yet, production processes are constantly being improved while the materials are evolving. New materials include glass, various ceramics and optical transparent plastics (Gibson, Rosen, & Stucker, 2010; Huson, 2010). One example of the new functional possibilities is the manufacturing of topologically optimized parts. Demonstrating this, Figure 1 shows an AM-built part that is up to 50% lighter than their conventionally-made equivalent while still complying with mechanical requirements (Wohlers, 2010).

Because AM does not need an investment in molds, each product can be unique in shape and functionality. This gives way to Mass Customization and Products on Demand. High-profile design companies and online service providers are demonstrating how AM can be used to manufacture end products and how the complexity and durability

Figure 1. 3D printed optimized aircraft part and original machined part (Boeing and University of Technology Hamburg-Harburg).

of products is increased without affecting the price (Freedom of Creation, 2011, Shapeways, 2011). We intent to address the gap between the possibilities of AM and available design methods and tools. Despite a growing body of knowledge concerning the technological challenges, very little research has been performed on the methods that allow designers to deal with this game changer. For example, at present, industrial design students apprehend a classic manufacturing engineering methodology where mold-based production techniques are at the forefront: decreasing the shapes complexity and increasing the homogeneity reduce the cost of a mold, and thus the cost price of the final product. The Roadmap for Additive Manufacturing (Bourell, Leu, & Rosen, 2009) recommends the development of new methods in order to benefit to the full extent from the opportunities that AM has to offer.

In this paper, we present a research approach through a number of multi-method research cycles. We hope this allows the design research community to consider the technological advantages as well as the anticipated changes in the design process. It will first present two important backgrounds: AM technology affordances and products on demand. Then, the research method is discussed. After this, preliminary results are shown, followed by a discussion and conclusions.

BACKGROUNDS

AM TECHNOLOGY AFFORDANCES

AM manufacturers claim that this fabrication means yields many technological benefits. In order to reason on the technology affordances that AM enables, we base our approach on Olson's Three Link Chain Model (3LCM), which originated from the material science domain (Olson, 1997). This model, illustrated in Figure 2, considers the linear relationships between the elements performance, properties, structure, and process. The performance is the behavior of the product to be designed. This behavior is, to some extent, included in a list of requirements by the designer. To achieve the desired behavior of the product, the designer can determine specific properties for the product's parts.

Figure 2. Olson's three link chain model (Olson, 1997).

These properties can be based on quantifiable desired behavior, such as maximum weight or strength, or less easy to quantify behavior, such as visual properties. The structure is the physical layout that directly controls the properties of the product. These structures can be on the scale of product features, such as handles, ribs, and cooling elements, or smaller, in the form of cell structures that build up bigger elements or, even smaller, on the material level, the density or structure of the material. Finally, processing represents a specific manufacturing method.

In the original article, 3LCM links material science to material engineering. Analysis of materials follows the deductive path, by investigating the material's structure that follows from its processing and deducing the properties and eventually the performance by cause and effect logic. Complementary, material engineering follows an inductive path by determining the desired performance and properties, the material structures that comply with this performance and processes that result in the desired structures. Usually, a design process does not follow any of these two directions through the framework linearly but by an iterative process where both induction and deduction plays an important role.

In line with the Design for Additive Manufacturing framework proposed by Rosen (2007), we adopt the 3LCM as a reasoning framework for design. The distinction between processing, structure and properties allows an expressive reasoning model to consider the benefits of AM, such as lightweight structures, material behavior in graded materials and the influence of the fabrication means on such phenomena.

When used for DfAM instead of material science, the meaning of the model remains the same but the context changes. Traversing from performance to processing represents a design process where, starting with a desired performance, a choice is made for the manufacturing process. Following this inductive path, depending on the needed structure, a suitable AM process for manufacturing can be selected that is able to create the needed structure. The deductive path can also be taken, which will be in the form of a simulation. Starting with an AM technology, a designer can deduce what structures a specific AM process can produce. These structures influence the product's properties and thus it can be reasoned whether the performance of the product will be satisfying.

Rosen's interpretation of the 3LCM is primarily focused on the design of new structures, which are only possible to create with AM. However, we increase the scope of the paradigm, as AM affords a larger variety of phenomena (e.g. graded materials and electrical conductivity). A full discussion on this scope is found in (Doubrovski, Geraedts, & Verlinden, 2011).

PRODUCTS ON DEMAND

In the near future, when AM has been fully developed by an integration of printing, robotics and material science, it will establish Products on Demand. AM allows personalized or customized products and (spare) parts that can economically and functionally meet products made with the traditional production techniques like injection molding. Piller (2005) explains that customization can bring benefits to the user not only by the resulting product but also by the process of customization itself.

Traditionally, products are based on one design that is produced in large series in a centralized manner. Every user gets an identical product with very little space for personal modifications, if any. Figure 3A illustrates this flow from designer to user.

During the last decade, examples have occurred where a customer can search his or her desired product in a digital catalogue, adapt it, and send the resulting file to a firm to fabricate it. In this scenario the designer no longer designs a product, but a product basis and a configurator that allows the user to configure the product. The result is a unique product for each user but within the boundaries set by the designer in the configurator. This flow is illustrated in Figure 3B. One example of such a configurable product is the 'Light Poem' from Shapeways (Shapeways, 2011), shown in Figure 4. Users can choose a text that is converted to form the built structure of a lamp shade which is produced with AM. The configurator and a produced lamp are shown in Figure 3

A: Traditional workflow for design and manufacturing

B: Workflow for configurable products

C: New workflow for AM products on demand

Figure 3. Different workflows for products considering customization.

Figure 4. Online configurator for the Light Poem and the final product (Shapeways, 2011).

In the workflow proposed in Figure 3C, the user inputs data in the customizable design. This data can for example be in the form of user-selected functional features, scanned anthropometric data, or aesthetic features. The critical and challenging step in this workflow is the processing of the user data into a producible design. This could be the fitting of the scanned data to a product basis or converting the individually requested functions into a product that functions properly as a whole.

Products on Demand in logistics also give way for the “long tail” approach (Anderson, 2006). Practice has shown that the total sales of the less popular products can add up to be more than the sales of a selection of top products. This is not only relevant to customizable products but also for the production of small series of products in general. Once individual products can be produced locally, the limitations of having to store the products is eliminated and the range of available products to the customer increases dramatically. Already we find that AM is often used for the production of small series (Wohlers, 2010). The introduction of new processes consequently brings new liability issues. The way legislation will adapt to this new process is still unclear but computer aided verification methods are already proposed (Jones & Wimpenny, 2009).

TOWARDS A DESIGN METHOD FOR ON-DEMAND ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF OPTIMAL PRODUCTS

AM will have a big influence on both the products and their development cycle. This includes changes in how products look, feel and function but also the way they are designed, produced, distributed, consumed and recycled. We formulated the following research questions:

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main research question of this investigation is: *How will designers adapt or change their way of working to a process where Additive Manufacturing is an integrated part?*

Based on the two perspectives described in the previous chapter, this can be decomposed in the following sub questions:

- How will a new DfAM method influence the digital and hardware domain to create new products, product-service combinations and business models
- How should the DfAM method and AM technology be integrated?
- Which limitations of the AM technologies for product design must be tackled and how?

To operationalize these issues, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

- A DfAM method that combines the unique capabilities of AM in technological and on-demand aspects will enable designers to create completely new products and product-service combinations.
- Olson’s 3LCM is a good basis for the technological aspects of a to-be-developed DfAM method.
- A DfAM method-tool combination that enables designers to fully benefit from the possibilities of AM does not exist, neither an AM system that is built for this purpose.

Figure 5. Proposed approach to investigate AM for design.

We present a research framework that explores these consequences and aims to develop new methods for designers to cope with these game changers. In line with (Eckert & Stacey, 2004), this requires to develop a better understanding of how designers could use this technology to design not only better but also completely new products. The presented research framework comprises five phases which are illustrated in Figure 5. Each of the phases consists of an individual research method, treating different topics and objectives, as discussed below.

PHASE A: RESEARCH CLARIFICATION

AM is a broad term and can enable changes on many levels in products and the design process. The goal of this phase is to investigate how AM and relevant technologies are evolving and how they could be applied into design practice. This phase includes a literature review, interviews as well as workshops with experts from the fields of topological optimization, CAD, AM, material industry, and design practice. The result will be a state of the art overview of AM technologies and existing tools and methods to treat these aspects.

PHASE B: ENGINEERING STUDY

Very little is known about the influence of AM technology on new product development in terms of the physical properties and functionality. Our approach to address this question is to include a series of design acts which will yield “new opportunities for generating knowledge, which cannot be derived otherwise” (Horvath, 2008). Such a research cycle with a design act is typified as design inclusive research and is included between the deduction and verification, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Research cycle of design inclusive research (Horvath, 2008).

In this phase the research cycle will focus on specific aspects of processes, structures and properties of AM. The design inclusion will hold the conception, design and prototyping of novel constructions. Based on findings in Phase A, we will focus on developing compliant and lightweight structures, as well as objects with particular visual properties. The design inclusion will also support to gain insight in the limitations of AM. In return, this will allow us to express necessary fields of improvements in AM technology.

PHASE C: THEORY DEVELOPMENT

A tool-method combination will be conceptualized resulting in a Design for Additive Manufacturing (DfAM) framework. This requires the design of computational support as well as process enhancement. Among the few researchers who have approached DfAM, Rosen (2007), has made a significant contribution by applying the 3LCM to a DfAM paradigm, and devised an initial method, including Design, CAD, and manufacturing (cf. Figure 7). We will base our framework on the same paradigm but, following the results from Phase B, we aim to apply this on a broader scope of properties and structures, and make this available for product designers.

Figure 7. Rosen's DFAM system and method (D. W. Rosen, 2007).

PHASE D: VERIFICATION

In order to verify the developed theory and test the hypotheses, in this phase we place the developed theory in the perspective of “Products on Demand”. While Phase B was focused on ‘how’ new products can be created, this phase focuses on the question ‘what’ products and product-service combinations could be implemented. We will validate the methods and tools by qualitative studies, involving experiments with designers, following the principles of Research in Design Context, as described by Horvath (2008). This requires a careful selection of

contexts, which reflect the value chains depicted in Section 2.

PHASE E: GENERALIZATION

As the possibilities of AM go beyond the discussed and tested topics, in this phase we will aim to generalize the developed theory. The value of the 3LCM and the developed methods and tools will to be evaluated to find their value as a general DfAM method for products on demand. The generalization will predominantly be argumentative, because such a new design method has influence on many aspects of the design and design process. It requires consideration of NPD and innovation management theories, such as radical innovation (Verganti, 2008).

EARLY FINDINGS

Through the scope of the 3LCM paradigm, a comprehensive state of the art of investigation was initiated based on the knowledge domains of engineering and computer graphics and is presented in by Doubrovski et al. (2011). We found three challenging principles that link structures to properties and could have an effect of products in the future: lightweight shapes and structures, compliant structures, and visual properties. Each of these are briefly discussed below.

OPTIMAL/ LIGHTWEIGHT SHAPES AND STRUCTURES

Shapes can be generated that are optimized for strength and material volume. Examples such as discussed the introduction demonstrate structures that are up to 50% lighter than their conventionally-made equivalent, while still fulfilling mechanical requirements (Wohlert, 2010).

Complexity in the millimeter-scale allows the creation of cellular structures which offer the advantage of high strength accompanied by a low mass. Furthermore these structures can provide good energy absorption and thermal and acoustic insulation properties (Williams, Mistree, & Rosen, 2005). Although this combination of AM and optimal structures is promising, a streamlined process for the design and production of lightweight products using AM is lacking.

COMPLIANT STRUCTURES

Opposed to maximum stiffness, in some cases it is preferred to achieve a certain amount of compliance in a structure. In literature, such desired deformation behavior is approached on the level of micro, meso and macro structures. Example applications include footwear (Bickel et al., 2010), gripper design (Zhou, 2010), and morphing airfoil (Chu, Graf, & D. W. Rosen, 2008). A commercial application is found in a robotic gripper, depicted in Figure 8. However, the main phenomenon of compliance in AM needs more insight in the modeling and fabrication, and present techniques do not fit in a generic design framework, accessible for designers.

Figure 8. Gripper with intrinsic compliant structures (Festo, 2011).

VISUAL PROPERTIES

Using the unique capabilities of multi material AM systems, Hašan et al. (2010) develop a process to model and fabricate structures with desired subsurface scattering. Visual properties in the field of Industrial Design Engineering are considered to be just as important as mechanical properties, and this phenomenon requires further study.

Figure 9. Tiles with graded materials to influence subsurface scattering - visual properties (Hašan et al., 2010).

FOCUS GROUP

A forerunning focus group has been organized to test the current application of Topology Optimization (TO) in the process of industrial design. The participants consisted of five 3rd year design students and a senior industrial designer with extensive experience with AM, for example the product shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Furniture sample of the participating designer.

During the focus group the participants modeled a product set-up in the TO tool “Topostruct” (Topostruct, 2011) and attempted to incorporate the outcome in their designs. Especially this last step showed to be problematic. The senior designer claimed that he uses TO results just as “inspiration” and meticulously creates his AM furniture from scratch.

The results show the gap between the lightweight possibilities of AM and industrial design needs to be addressed.

DISCUSSION

RESEARCH APPROACH

(Blessing & Chakrabarti, 2009) describe a Design Research Methodology (DRM) for the purpose of development of design support. They propose a framework consisting of four stages. A clarification stage that includes a literature analysis, a descriptive stage resulting in a better understanding of the current situation, a prescriptive stage in which support is developed, and a descriptive study to evaluate the developed support. Although we similarly aim to develop design support, our approach differs from the DRM. Because our newly developed methods can have consequences on many

aspects, these changes are far beyond the scope of the measurable. For this reason we do not aim to set up and measure success criteria, as described by (Blessing & Chakrabarti, 2009). In line with (Eckert & Stacey, 2004), we believe that for this research a fixation on measurable criteria could lead us to “miss the real issues by selecting over-specific methods.”

HYPOTHESES

We can preliminarily check our hypotheses using the findings from this paper.

The results from the focus group partly confirm our hypothesis that adequate tools DfAM do not exist. Also in literature we have found no evidence of a holistic DfAM method.

As we use the 3 Link Chain Model from the material science to approach the proposed DfAM method, it appears to be a valuable framework to deal with the physical and technological aspects of AM. However, as noted earlier, the on-demand aspects of AM are just as important. This means that during the Theory Development Phase the DfAM framework must be extended to the Products-on-Demand to domain to be successfully placed in this context during the Verification Phase.

The evaluation of the DfAM method itself and answering the research questions can be done after completing the phases of the research.

Understanding the consequences of our new method will be more important than looking at the result. For this Eckert & Stacey (2004) advice to look for acceptance in industry and to investigate how and why the tools are used.

CONCLUSIONS

Additive Manufacturing is considered to act as a game changer in New Product Development. We presented a research approach that is aimed at obtaining a better understanding in how this technology can change products and the way of working for designers. We tackle these questions by devising and evaluating new methods and tools. Prior to the research approach, we discuss the possibilities that AM enables. These are in the field of new product value chains (Products on Demand) and in the physical properties of the product. The three link chain model is used as a paradigm to treat the physical properties.

The proposed research approach consists of five phases. The research clarification phase includes a literature review resulting in a state of the art. The Engineering study holds several cycles of design inclusive research, aimed at generating new knowledge through the design and prototyping of novel constructions using AM. In the Theory Development phase we conceptualize a tool-method combination that results in a DfAM framework. This framework is verified in the perspective of Products on Demand by several cycles of research in design context. In the Generalization phase we formulate the value of the developed tools and methods. Finally, we discuss how this research approach fits within design research literature. Also we present preliminary results of the literature review and a forerunning focus group which confirms our hypothesis that adequate tools for industrial designers to create products with optimized lightweight structures do not exist.

Next to the technological and economic issues, the acceptance of AM technology among designers, industry and users is often considered as the limiting factor (Wohlert, 2010). Our objective is to break this by introducing a successful DfAM method.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, C. (2006). *The Long Tail: Why the Future of Business is Selling Less of More*. Hyperion.
- Bickel, B., Bäcker, M., Otaduy, M. a, Lee, H. R., Pfister, H., Gross, M., & Matusik, W. (2010). Design and fabrication of materials with desired deformation behavior. *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, 29(4).
- Blessing, L., & Chakrabarti, A. (2009). *DRM, a design research methodology*. Springer Verlag.
- Bourell, D. L., Leu, M., & Rosen, DW. (2009). *Roadmap for Additive Manufacturing: Identifying the Future of Freeform Processing*. The University of Texas Austin. The University of Texas, Austin.
- Chu, C., Graf, G., & Rosen, D. W. (2008). Design for Additive Manufacturing of Cellular Structures. *Computer-Aided Design and Applications*, 5(5), 686-696.
- Doubrovski, E. L., Geraedts, J. M. P., & Verlinden, J. C. (2011). Optimal Design for Additive Manufacturing: Opportunities and Challenges. *Proceedings of the ASME 2011 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference IDETC/CIE 2011*
- Eckert, C. M., Stacey, M. K. and Clarkson, P. J. (2004). "The Lure of the Measurable in Design Research." *Proceedings of International Design Conference*, May 18-21, Dubrovnik, Croatia, 21-26.
- Festo. (2011) Retrieved February 2, 2011, from http://www.festo.com/cms/en-ca_ca/10304.htm
- Freedom of Creation. (2011). Retrieved February 2, 2011, from <http://www.freedomofcreation.com/>
- Gibson, I., Rosen, David, & Stucker, B. (2010). *Additive Manufacturing Technologies: Rapid Prototyping to Direct Digital Manufacturing*. Media. New York, NY: Springer Science Business Media.
- Hašan, M., Fuchs, M., Matusik, W., Pfister, H., & Rusinkiewicz, S. (2010). Physical reproduction of materials with specified subsurface scattering. *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, 29(4), 1.
- Horvath, I. (2008). Differences between "research in design context" and "design inclusive research" in the domain of industrial design engineering. *Journal of Design Research*, 7(1), 61.
- Huson, D. (2010). The digital fabrication of ceramics by 3D powder printing. *NIP26: International Conference on Digital Printing Technologies and Digital Fabrication 2010* (Vol. 26, pp. 545-548). Society for Imaging Science and Technology.
- Jones, J., & Wimpenny, D. (2009). *Customised rapid manufactured parts: Technology and case studies from the custom-fit project*. Retrieved April 6, 2011, from http://edge.rit.edu/content/P10551/public/SFF/SFF_2009_Proceedings/2009_SFF_Papers/2009-57-Jones.pdf
- Olson, G. B. (1997). Computational Design of Hierarchically Structured Materials. *Science*, 277(5330), 1237-1242. doi:10.1126/science.277.5330.1237
- Piller, F. T. (2004). Mass customization: reflections on the state of the concept. *International Journal of Flexible Manufacturing Systems*, 16(4), 313-334. Springer.
- Rosen, D. W. (2007). Computer-aided design for additive manufacturing of cellular Structures. *Computer-Aided Design & Applications*, 4(5), 585-594. Citeseer.
- Shapeways. (2011). Retrieved February 2, 2011, from <http://www.shapeways.com>
- Topostruct. (2011). Retrieved February 2, 2011, from http://sawapan.eu/sections/section79_topostruct/download.html
- Verganti, R. (2008). Design, Meanings, and Radical Innovation: A Metamodel and a Research Agenda. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 25(5), 436-456.
- Williams, C. B., Mistree, F., & Rosen, D. W. (2005). Investigation of Solid Freeform Fabrication Processes for the Manufacture of Parts with Designed Mesostructure. *Proceedings of the ASME 2005 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference*. Long Beach, California USA, DETC2005-84832.
- Wohlert, T. (2010). *Wohlert Report 2010*. Wohlert Associates (Vol. 29, pp. 234-245).
- Zhou, H. (2010). Topology Optimization of Compliant Mechanisms Using Hybrid Discretization Model. *Proceedings of the ASME 2010 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference*. Montreal, Quebec, Canada. DETC2010-28150.